

EXTERIOR INDICATORS OF COWS IN EXPERIMENTAL**Toshtemirov Nodirbek Muhiddin o'g'li**

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Abstract: *The studies determined the growth and development indicators of Simmental cows. The level of body development of group II cows was slightly higher than that of group I cows, as indicated by the body size indicators. In particular, it was found that group II cows had higher indicators than group I: withers height by an average of 1.5 cm, rump height by 0.9 cm, chest width by 1.7 cm, chest circumference by 1.0 cm, chest depth by 4.0 cm, body length by 1.4 cm, back bone width by 1.3 cm, and foot circumference by 0.5 cm.*

Примечание:

В исследовании были определены показатели роста и развития коров симментальской породы. Показатели телосложения также свидетельствуют о том, что уровень развития тела коров II группы несколько выше, чем у коров I группы. В частности, были выявлены высокие значения высоты коров II группы в среднем на 1,5 см выше, чем у коров I группы, высоты ягодиц 0,9 см, ширины грудной клетки 1,7 см, окружности грудной клетки 1,0 см, глубины грудной клетки 4,0 см, косой длины тела 1,4 см, ширины задней части бедра 1,3 см, окружности икры 0,5 см.

Relevance of the topic.

Growth and development management has always been a problem in

zootechnical practice. Individual development occurs as a result of complex interactions in a specific external environment, where the genetic basis of the animal and its hereditary basis are implemented. Animal development is a chain of continuous changes in quantitative and qualitative characteristics. The exterior of cows is of great importance in creating productive dairy herds. Cows with a balanced exterior usually have a milk type and are productive. In determining the positive correlation between the exterior of cows and milk productivity, it is important to study the characteristics of the exterior, and based on the results obtained, it is of great practical importance to carry out selection work on their exterior for optimal characteristics.

Research location and methods. The research was conducted on cows from the Simmental cattle herd of the “K-Eldor” breeding farm in the Pastdargam district of the Samarkand region. Ten cows were selected for the experiment.

Research results. We studied the body dimensions of cows in the experimental groups, the results of which are presented in Table 1.

Table - 1

Body dimensions of cows in the experimental group, cm (n=10)

Indicators	Groups			
	I		II	
	$\bar{X} \pm S\bar{x}$	Cv,%	$\bar{X} \pm S\bar{x}$	Cv,%
Rain height	135,4±1,54	4,25	136,9±1,42	3,88
Height of the rump	139,2±1,42	3,81	140,1±1,53	4,08
Chest width	73,7±1,40	7,10	75,4±1,34	6,64
Chest circumference	53,0±1,12	7,9	54,0±1,23	8,52
Chest depth	211,5±3,62	6,40	215,5±2,88	5,00

Oblique length of the body	160,4±1,2	2,8	161,8±1,04	2,40
Posterior humerus width	53,3±0,9	6,31	54,6±1,0	6,85
Wheelbase	22,1±0,24	4,06	22,6±0,18	2,98

As can be seen from the data in Table 1, the level of body development of cows in Group II was slightly higher than that of cows in Group I, as indicated by body size indicators. In particular, the height at the withers of cows in Group II was on average 1.5 cm higher than that of cows in Group I, the height of the rump was 0.9 cm, the width of the chest was 1.7 cm, the circumference of the chest was 1.0 cm, the depth of the chest was 4.0 cm, the length of the body was 1.4 cm, the width of the hindquarters was 1.3 cm, and the circumference of the legs was 0.5 cm higher.

Conclusion.

Our studies revealed that the body of Holstein cows imported from abroad was well-developed, and at high feeding levels their external dimensions were slightly higher, indicating that they belonged to the dairy type.

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